

Germination and vigor of hydrated rice seeds after 3 periods of storage. Tamil Nadu, India.

Cultivar duration	Parameter	Initial	After storage						Biological loss (%)			
			8 mo		12 mo		32 mo		Control	Hydrated		
			Control	Hydrated	Control	Hydrated	Control	Hydrated				
Short	Germination (%)	86	82	90	<i>ADT31</i>		73	89	45	85	47.7	1.2
	Root length (cm)	19.5	17.6	22.1	15.0	20.0	9.2	17.8	52.8	8.7		
Medium	Germination (%)	90	84	95	<i>Bhavani</i>		75	86	16	85	82.2	5.6
	Root length (cm)	18.2	16.0	17.6	15.0	19.5	10.4	18.2	42.8	–		
Long	Germination (%)	89	86	94	<i>CO40</i>		78	88	27	87	69.7	2.2
	Root length (cm)	20.7	18.9	21.1	17.7	20.2	11.5	19.0	44.4	8.2		

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soil microbiology

Influence of wild plant and crop residues on rice yield

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Plant residues and farmyard manure are added to soils to improve their organic matter content and productivity. This traditional agricultural practice has primarily been used to increase soil humus content, water-holding capacity, water infiltration rate, aeration, and porosity; to ameliorate soil temperature; and to supply some essential plant nutrients.

In a pot study, we evaluated the effect of incorporating residues of mesquite (*Prosopis glandulosa*), withania (*Withania somnifera*), and country mallow (*Abutilon indicum*) with rice (*Oryza sativa*) husks and wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) and rice straw, neem (*Azadirachta indicum*) leaves, and farmyard manure on straw and grain yields of rice. Soil had pH 7.6, 0.95%

organic C, 0.073% N, 9.7% CaCO₃, 0.15% TSS. Each pot held 8 kg soil.

For the wild plants, treatments were 3 g residue/kg soil (about 6 t/ha) plus 25 mg N/kg (about 50 kg N/ha). For the crop residues, treatments were 3 g residue/kg soil plus 50 mg N/kg soil. Each pot also received 25 mg P/kg soil. Rice cultivar Shadab was transplanted at 4 seedlings/pot. Pots were arranged in a randomized block design with four replications. N application was lower for the wild plants because their very high antibiotic activities tended to inhibit nitrification.

Effect of incorporating plant residues on rice straw and grain yields.^a

Treatment ^b (g/pot)	Straw yield	Grain yield (g/pot)
Control (no residue)	17.45 c	11.70 b
Mesquite	28.80 a	24.97 a
Withania	23.92 b	19.62 a
Country mallow	24.62 b	22.00 a
Rice husk	16.05 c	11.62 b
Wheat straw	16.92 c	10.75 b
Rice straw	18.05 c	12.10 b
Neem leaf	25.22 b	20.67 a
Farmyard manure	17.92 c	10.22 b

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different (DMRT p<0.5). ^b Plant residue and farmyard manure were applied at 3 g/kg soil.

Straw and grain yield increased significantly with incorporation of mesquite, withania, and country mallow residues, and of neem leaf (see table). ■

Effect of seeding rate on dry matter production and nitrogen accumulation of *Sesbania rostrata*

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Increased crop seeding rates result in increased plant competition for nutrients and light. We evaluated the effect of different seeding rates on dry matter production and N accumulation in *Sesbania rostrata*, a stem-nodulating legume and potential green manure crop for lowland rice.

The field experiment was conducted in 1987 wet season. Soil was a Maahas clay (Tropaquept) with pH 6.3; 11 g organic C/kg; 1.2 g total N/kg; and cation exchange capacity, 34 cmol/kg. P (20 kg/ha) as single superphosphate was broadcast and incorporated before seeding. Seeding rates were 20, 30, 40, and 50 kg sesbania seeds/ha, laid out in a factorial randomized complete block design with four replications. Plot size was 20 m².

Sesbania seeds pretreated for 30 min with concentrated sulfuric acid were broadcast into well-leveled, water-saturated soil. The field was kept saturated to 7 d after seeding, then flooded to 0.05 m.

Sesbania was harvested 45 d after seeding. Plant fresh and dry weights were measured and plant density determined from a 7-m² area. A subsample (4 × 1 m per plot) was taken to determine leaf and stem dry matter separately and to analyze N concentrations in leaf and stem. Total N accumulation was calculated.

N concentrations in leaf and stem did not differ significantly with seeding rate (see table). Seeding at 40 kg/ha gave the highest total N accumulation per plant (114 kg N/ha), and highest fresh and dry matter production. Seeding at 50 kg/ha gave lower fresh and dry matter production and N accumulation than seeding at 40 kg/ha.